
102. The heart of the Milky Way

A RECENT PAPER based on Gaia Data Release 3, entitled ‘The Poor Old Heart of the Milky Way’ (Rix et al., 2022), caught my attention as providing a fascinating and substantial advance in understanding the earliest phases of our Galaxy’s formation.

OUR GALAXY comprises a flattened disk with a number of spiral arms, an extended massive halo, and a spherical bulge with an associated bar-like extension. The present Λ CDM (cold-dark matter) cosmology can explain an overall picture. But many details are still unclear: Are spiral arms transient or long-lasting? Why is the disk warped? What is the origin of its central bar?

Our knowledge of the spherical halo has advanced enormously over the past two decades (through a combination of astrometric, photometric, and spectroscopic surveys): for example, we know that tidal debris from the disrupted Sagittarius dwarf satellite dominates from 20–50 kpc, with stars mostly on highly inclined orbits. Between 5–25 kpc the Gaia–Sausage–Enceladus satellite debris dominates, with stars on highly eccentric orbits. And a growing number of distinct but less-prominent accreted components are also being identified.

MEANWHILE, details of the inner Galaxy have proven much more elusive, complicated by extinction and the large distances of the stellar populations.

Amongst recent advances, Gaia data have been used to clarify the properties of inner globular clusters as tracers of a very old Galaxy component, with ‘Kraken’ (Kruijssen et al. 2020) and ‘Koala’ (Forbes 2020) having been identified as possible examples of early accretion.

Belokurov & Kravtsov (2022) used Gaia EDR3 data to reconstruct stellar kinematics in the inner Galaxy down to metallicities of -1.5 in $[M/H]$, and identified an *in situ* proto-Galactic structure ‘Aurora’. The constituent stars shows little net rotation, and may have preceded the Milky Way’s ancient disk.

Conroy et al. (2022) used kinematics and ages from EDR3 and the Hectochelle H3 survey to identify proto-Galactic stars down to -2.5 in $[M/H]$ with ages ≥ 13 Gyr.

THE EARLIEST PHASES of our Galaxy’s star-formation and enrichment history are reflected in the orbits and abundances of these old metal-poor stars. But to be more quantitative about how our Galaxy came into existence, we need to phrase our objectives more precisely. Here, I will borrow extensively from the introduction given by Rix et al. (2022).

In the context of the hierarchical formation of massive disk galaxies, the oldest and most metal-poor stars are expected to be a mix that either formed within one of the main overdensities which coalesced early on to form the proto-Galaxy (termed *in situ* formation), or formed early on in distinct satellite galaxies that eventually merged with the main body (accreted formation).

If the *in situ* stars formed in a more massive potential well than the accreted stars, the difference in origin should also be reflected in their abundance patterns, such as $[\alpha/Fe]$ vs $[Fe/H]$. However, at early epochs, this distinction may be blurred, with high-resolution simulations of the formation of Milky Way-like galaxies showing that fragments of comparable mass may rapidly coalesce early on (say, $z > 4$) in a sequence of major mergers.

ONE CHOICE IN terminology could then be to label only the most massive fragment as the *in situ* component, and to label all others as accreted – even though, together, the latter may constitute the majority of the total mass. But the same simulations show that, later on, it may not be possible to differentiate what was *in situ* and what was accreted at very early epochs.

Alternatively, one could label collectively all the major pieces that coalesced very early on, say at $z \geq 5$, as the proto-Galaxy, and then differentiate subsequent additions at slightly later epochs (say, $z < 3$) either as *in situ* (if the material was brought in as gas), or as accreted (if the stars formed in a distinct potential well that then subsequently merged).

Partly as a result of their findings, Rix et al. (2022) adopted the second terminology, referring to the oldest parts of the Milky Way as the proto-Galaxy, without trying to single out one of the contributing pieces as *in situ*.

WITHIN THIS FRAMEWORK, Rix et al. (2022) set out to derive a more comprehensive picture of the dynamical properties of metal-poor stars in the inner Galaxy (within 5 kpc), drawing on ‘... *the immense wealth of new information that Gaia DR3 now affords*’.

They selected giant stars within 30° of the Galactic centre, derived $[M/H]$ estimates from the BP/RP spectra, and combined them with Gaia’s RVS velocities to obtain Galactic orbits for 1.5 million stars in the inner Galaxy.

Their primary goal was to see whether there is an extensive ancient and metal-poor stellar population at the ‘heart’ of the Milky Way. And to learn whether the bulk of these stars are a tightly bound proto-Galactic population, rather than stars accreted from more distant satellites (whose location in the inner Galaxy merely reflects the pericentre phase of orbits that take them out to the ‘classical’ halo at distances beyond the solar radius).

THEY WERE ABLE to identify metal-poor samples of stars towards the inner Galaxy a factor 100 larger in size than previously available: specifically, more than 4000 stars with $[M/H] < -2$, some 20 000 with $[M/H] < -1.5$, and 70 000 with $[M/H] < -1$.

Their samples reveal a large metal-poor population ($[M/H] < -1.5$) in the inner few kpc of the Galaxy. Various lines of argument imply that this population is centrally concentrated: for example, the parallax distribution (shown here) implies that most stars are within 5 kpc of the Galactic centre. And their reconstructed orbits show that most have apocenters within 5 kpc.

These orbits also imply that most of this population could not have been identified in many of the previous surveys that focused on Galactic radii $\lesssim 5$ kpc. At the same time, their analysis shows that a minority (but nonetheless a large number) of stars with $[M/H] < -1.2$ currently in the inner Galaxy are on high-eccentricity orbits that can take them to > 10 kpc. These are presumably members of the accreted halo, simply found near the pericentre of their orbits.

Using the sample members with detailed abundances from SDSS (DR17), in particular $[\alpha/Fe]$, $[Al/Fe]$

and $[Mn/Fe]$, they explored which of these stars have abundance patterns attributable to a proto-Galactic (or *in situ*) origin, as opposed to an accreted origin. They found that almost all stars that remain tightly bound within the inner Galaxy, say with apocentres within the solar radius, have abundances that suggest a proto-Galactic origin. Stars on high-eccentricity orbits with apocentres above 10 kpc show abundances typical of accreted stars; presumably pericentric members of the disrupted Gaia–Sausage–Enceladus.

By considering, for each mono-abundance population, the mean ratio of their angular momentum to the total action, they also quantified their net Galactic rotation, and the extent to which they resemble disk-like orbits. They found that only the most metal-poor members, $[M/H] < -2$, show no rotation, while populations with higher $[M/H]$ also have higher rotation.

ALL OF THIS, they conclude, fits a picture in which this metal-poor heart of the Milky Way constitutes the most ancient ‘proto-Galactic’ component of our Galaxy. Their findings are worth setting out in detail (Rix et al. 2022; Section 4).

Much of their low-metallicity population is confined to Galactic radii within the solar radius, i.e. tightly bound at the bottom of the Galaxy’s potential well, arguing against an origin through accretion from a once-distant satellite. And the vast majority of stars with $[M/H] < -1.5$ are distinctly α -enhanced, arguing for rapid enrichment in a deep potential well.

The total stellar mass seen at $[M/H] < -1.5$ within 5 kpc corresponds to $\sim 5 \times 10^7 M_\odot$. But obvious dust obscuration implies a large correction, in turn suggesting that the total stellar mass of this metal-poor heart of the Milky Way is much higher, $M_* \gtrsim 10^8 M_\odot$. Such a high mass of strongly α -enhanced stars at such low $[M/H]$ is most likely to occur at the centre of a rather massive halo, rather than within a low-mass satellite system.

Their findings of a correlation between rotation and increasing metallicity is expected if star formation occurs – as time goes on – in gas that has increasingly settled into a disk, as shown in recent simulations of disk galaxy formation (Gurvich et al. 2022).

Finally, much of this central component has $[M/H]$ values well below that of the centrally concentrated, α -enhanced, thick disk, whose oldest members (at around -1 in $[M/H]$) have ages of around 12.5 Gyr. If much of this metal-poor component predates chemically, and therefore temporally, the oldest α -enhanced disk, it must have formed before that, corresponding to $z \gtrsim 5$. The stellar population at the heart of the Milky Way should therefore be, almost exclusively, ancient.

IT WILL END by quoting Rix et al. (2022), that their analysis ‘... *reflects the astounding information content of the Gaia DR3 data, particularly the B_p/R_p spectra*’.